

PERCEPTION AND CONSEQUENCES OF CRUDE OIL PIPELINE VANDALISM IN SOUTHERN IJAW LOCAL GOVERNMENT OF BAYELSA STATE

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Abstract

Oil pipeline vandalism is a global phenomenon that has created huge economic challenges to countries of the world, Nigeria inclusive. This study therefore examined the perception and consequences of oil pipeline vandalism in Southern Ijaw Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. The study was anchored on Routine Activity Theory (RAT) and Frustration-Aggression Theory (FAT). The study employed cross sectional descriptive survey research design with questionnaire and In-depth interview as instruments of data collection. A sample size of 354 was chosen through Taro Yamane statistical method from the population of 31941. Snobal and purposive smapling method was utilized. Data analysis was done using univariate level using descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution and Relative Importance Index (RII). The study revealed that unfulfilled expectations, or promises, corrupt leadership, bureaucratic bottleneck, greed, youthful exuberance, mechanical failures, inadequate compensation, poor resources management and sabotage were perceived to be the causes of crude oil pipeline vandalism in the study area. With respect to perception, the study revealed that people who engage in crude oil pipeline vandalism were poor and tends to make quick money, take advantage of weak control mechanism and respond to peer group influence among others. The study also revealed that large scale death wastage of government revenues, environmental pollution, violence, power outage, fuel scarcity, population displacement among others were part of the consequences of crude oil pipeline vandalism. The suggested strategies for crude oil pipeline vandalism including provision of adequate and well equipped security, community based surveillance, empowerment and provision of employment for youths and jobless residents. The study concluded that crude oil pipeline vandalism portends great danger for the economy and security of the nation. Hence the study recommends that government at all levels should organize enlightenment programmes to educate residents on the grave consequences of crude oil pipeline vandalism, and then create job opportunities, involve host communities in surveillance and empower residents through skill acquisitions and provision of soft loan facilities in the study area. Also Security agencies should be well equipped with more advanced equipment to adequately safeguard against crude oil pipeline vandalism.

Keywords: Crude Oil, Pipelines, Perception, Consequences, Vandalism, Niger Delta, Southern Nigeria.

Introduction

Since the discovery of crude oil and natural gas (ONG) in the Niger Delta Region in 1956, the socio-economic and political well-being of the people of the region has deteriorated, (Semenitari & Ibim, 2018). This is due mainly to environmental degradation caused by unregulated ONG exploration and production activities. Infact, unemployment, criminal and political violent activities in the Niger Delta have seriously affected the region (Etekpe, Inyang, and Ekanem, 2012). Given the proximity and accessibility of the region' s energy infrastructure to inhabitants, oil pipeline vandalism or illegal bunkering has been on the increase and has caused displacement and social disintegration of communities within the region (Etekpe, Inyang, and Ekanem, 2012). The pipeline is one of the effective means of an uninterrupted and steady supply of crude oil. This medium ensures that consumers get their product at the right time. This mode of transportation has existed for over a century and helps to reduce accidents, spillage, and environmental pollution. (Babatunde, 2010)

According to Brume (2016), vandalism is an action involving the deliberate destruction of public or private property. Within the civic domain, vandalism denotes willful destruction of public or government property in keeping with criminal or political intent. Oil pipeline vandalism, therefore, implies the deliberate breaking of oil pipelines with the intent to steal petroleum products or to sabotage the government. In Nigeria, oil pipeline vandalism has been perpetrated principally by criminal syndicates who are motivated by the desire to loot oil products for material gains. Crude oil pipeline vandalism is also known as oil bunkering, which is the act of drilling into the pipelines with the intent to steal products (Brume, 2016).

Nigeria' s pipeline infrastructure has been exposed to incessant attacks by militants and pipeline vandalizers across the country. The frequency of such attacks has been very alarming and is affecting the country' s economy. In fact, investors (domestically & internationally) have been losing interest in the country' s oil sector due to the vandalism and general insecurity. The implications on power generation and general socio-economic development of the nation is alarming and have made it difficult for business organizations to achieve their goals of being in business, (Brume, 2016).

The incidence of pipeline vandalism by Niger Delta Avengers and other militant groups has been on the increase in Nigeria and has continually affected oil production and the country' s output projection of 2.2million BPD, which has now dropped to less than a 1.1million BPD (CBN, 2016). Consequently, the gas supply for electricity generation and distribution has been seriously affected. In fact, business activities and economic growth has also been affected and this calls for immediate action.

Oil exploration activities commenced in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria in the early 1900s by a German entity referred to as the “Nigeria Bitumen Corporation” which started her exploratory activities in the Araromi area of then Western Nigeria but their activities were truncated by the outbreak of the World War I in 1914 (NNPC, 2015). Oil exploration activities thereafter started with the Shell D’ Arcy (the forerunner of Shell Petroleum Development Company, SPDC of Nigeria) in 1937 when Shell was awarded the sole concessionary rights covering the whole territory of Nigeria. Their activities were also interrupted by World War II but they resumed in 1947 and with concerted efforts, after several years and investment of over N30 million, the first commercial oil well was discovered in 1956 at Oloibiri in present Ogbia Local Government of Bayelsa State in the Niger Delta region.

This discovery opened up the oil industry in 1961 in Nigeria, bringing more oil firms like Agip, Mobil, Safrap (now Elf), Texaco, and Chevron to petroleum prospecting both in onshore/offshore areas of Nigeria. From then, “oil production rose from initial figures of 5,100 barrels per day (BPD) from the first well in Oloibiri to today’s production of over 25 million BPD, even though our OPEC quota specification is based on 2.15 million BPD” (Okaba, 2018). Between 1956 and 1958, more oil fields were discovered at Afam, Bonu, Ebubu, and Later Ugheli and Kokori, and the production capacity steadily rose. By this period, oil has become so prominent that the search for more of it had intensified in various communities in the region (Okaba, 2018).

The Niger Delta region is one of the richest oil-producing areas in Nigeria and the largest wetland in Africa. The region is estimated to have 37 billion barrels (bb) of oil reserves and 168 trillion cubic feet of gas deposits (Omotola, 2019). The oil sector account for over 90% of foreign exchange earnings for Nigeria and the bulk of it comes from the Niger Delta region. However, the region is also considered as one of the most oil impacted regions in the world due to poor regulated oil activities (Omotola, 2019; Raji & Abejide, 2013). A number of factors have contributed to the environmental degradation of the region over the years, and this includes gas flaring, industrial pollution, oil spillage, etc. (Raji & Abejide, 2013). Although government have made concerted efforts to promote development in the region for many years through the establishment of the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC), Oil Mineral Producing Areas Development Commission (OMPADC), Ministry of Niger delta (MND), and Amnesty program for the militants and improvements of revenue derivation for the oil-producing states in the region from 1 to 13% over the years, however, the impact of such developmental programme have been shown due to corruption and inconsistency in programmes implementations.

Over the years, crude oil spillage through pipeline vandalism is considered one of the major problems of the region. Rising cases of pipeline vandalism by militant groups have significantly

affected sources of revenues of government and oil companies operating in the region. The militants claimed to be fighting for the emancipation of the region from environmental neglect. Statistics have shown that Nigeria is losing well over 300,000 barrels per day (BPD) as a result of crude oil pipeline vandalism, which runs into billions of dollars in losses (James, 2014; NNPC, 2013). This has resulted in significant negative socioeconomic and environmental problems in the region with serious effects on human lives and farmlands. Against this background, this study seeks to examine the perception and consequences of crude oil pipeline vandalization in southern Ijaw Local Government.

Statement of the Problem

The activity of oil and gas in the Delta South Senatorial District has not only brought hardship to inhabitants of oil producing communities but severe health problems due to frequent pollution of the area as a result of oil pipeline vandalization. The region is frequently exposed to various forms of pollution and as a result, the inhabitants suffer both economic and, health problems. There is constant vandalization of the oil pipe line in spite of the security network put in place. This has led to the destruction of farmlands used for farming as well as the pollution of the water bodies used for fishing.

The major challenges of pipeline vandalism are poor policing and protection of pipeline infrastructure, political/militant agitation, and endemic corruption. However, the fundamental issues are the attendant consequences of pipeline vandalism such as a decline in Crude Oil revenue, scarcity of PMS, and decline in electricity generation which all affect business activities in Nigeria. The level at which the Nigerian pipeline are been vandalized and crude oil are been made away in large quantities has become a persistent problem and has unfortunately been carried out by even the political class. The story of vandalized pipelines in Nigeria is becoming concurrent, properties are vandalized by the leaders and no one says nor does anything about it. Is has been the main issue in the research work, pipeline vandalization.

This results into loss of economic means of livelihood as this has led to hunger, poverty and total hardship. The increasing rate of oil pipeline vandalization has led to the frequent exposure of the inhabitants of oil producing communities to various hazardous conditions which has led to the wide spread of water borne diseases, such as cholera, typhoid fever, cardiovascular diseases and skin infections. The prevalence of malnutrition and otlier deficiency diseases among children in the area is also worrisome.

Overall, oil pipeline Vandalisation constitutes a veritable threat to Nigeria' s national security the impact and implications of pipeline Vandalisation have been critically detrimental to the concerns of public safety and development in Nigeria. To say the least, therefore, the prevalence of oil pipeline Vandalisation in Nigeria over the years has presented the country with crucial

national security challenges, Onuoha, (2018). Although factors such as institutional weakness, lack of effective implementation of environmental laws were hypothesized as the causes of vandalism in the region, they are considered neither exhaustive nor confirmed as no available empirical evidence can be found confirming the asserted causes of vandalism in the area. Against this background, this study seeks to examine the perception and consequences of crude oil pipeline vandalization in southern Ijaw Local Government Bayelsa State.

Research Question

To achieve the above, the study came up with the following research questions. The research questions are stated as follows:

- i. What are the perceived causes of crude oil pipeline vandalization in the Southern Ijaw Local Government Area?
- ii. What are the perceptions of Southern Ijaw Local Government residents on crude oil pipeline vandalization?
- iii. What are the consequences of crude oil pipeline vandalization in the Southern Ijaw Local Government Area?
- iv. What are the suggested strategies to curb crude oil pipeline vandalization in Southern Ijaw Local Government Area?

Objectives of the Study

Based on the above-stated problems, the study came up with the following objectives. The specific objectives of the research work are to:

- i. examine the perceived causes of crude oil pipeline vandalization in Southern Ijaw Local Government Area.
- ii. examine the perceptions of Southern Ijaw Local Government residents on crude oil pipeline vandalization.
- iii. investigate the consequences of crude oil pipeline vandalization in Southern Ijaw Local Government Area.
- iv. investigate the suggested strategies to curb crude oil pipeline vandalization in Southern Ijaw Local Government Area.

Significance of the Study

The outcome of this research work will be of beneficial help to the nation as it will highlight the effect of vandalizing the country property, in this case, the vandalization of pipeline, on the economic development of this country, a highlight of its set back to the country.

This study will also assist the government and oil producing companies in understanding bases upon which it can perform better in its operations, how to handle difficulties that are presently confronting the region. Moreover, it will help to influence public opinion, deepen awareness, elicit ownership and generate support for the development processes in the region. It will help private organizations, Community Based Organizations, Faith-Based Organizations, and multinational companies in corporate social responsibility decisions.

Findings and recommendations will assist future research and serve as a reference document. Still, the knowledge derived from the studies will provide critical input for appropriate programmes and projects.

Scope of the Study

This study focuses on the perception and consequences of crude oil pipeline vandalization in Southern Ijaw local government. It covers both male and female residents of Southern Ijaw local government area of Bayelsa State.

Literature Review

Relevant and related literature are reviewed under the following subheadings:

Conceptual Review

Concept of crude oil pipeline vandalization

The concept of oil pipeline vandalism and oil sabotage are vital to discourse in this piece of work and as such to highlight details of their meaning for proper understanding. First, oil pipelines are the medium through which crude oil, natural gas, and industrial chemicals are transported (Chibuzor, Chukwujekwu, & Ekene, 2014). Oil pipelines are vital and sensible facilities that could cause inconceivable catastrophes during operation, transportation of petroleum product, or maintenance without a deliberate act of vandals or saboteurs. The concept of vandalism according to Chibuzor et al. (2014), is an illegal or unauthorized activity carried out jointly with different entities in the destruction of gas, petroleum, and chemical pipelines.

Umar and Othman (2017) describe vandalism as a thoughtful antagonistic behavior of unsatisfied and corrupt individuals aimed directly at an environmental object with a destructive motive of damaging properties and causing harm. Also, Christensen, Johnson, and Brookes (1992) describe oil vandalism as a “productive force that fought against the exploration of a capacity system” across the world. Even though different people or nations may have a contrary opinion to the concept of vandalism and what ‘acts’ constitute vandalism, the concept could be applied to different scenarios such as; play vandalism, for example, breaking of window panels, cars, and

other people's facilities, tactical vandalism which includes, sabotage at the workplace or organizational facilities (Umar & Othman, 2017), vandalism as a source of revenge, where individuals feel cheated (vindictive behaviour) and vandalism out of frustration, anger and exasperation (malicious vandalism) (Umar & Othman, 2017). Also, Aishatu, Chukwudi, and Hauwa' u (2016) describe vandalism from the civil realm as the wilful destruction of public or government property in keeping with criminal or political intent. While vandalism in the oil and gas industries implies the breaking of oil pipelines to scoop petroleum products for personal and or group use.

However, vandalism in most developing countries is aimed to sabotage the government and or oil and gas operating companies (Aishatu et al. 2016), when felt neglected as the case may be. The concept of sabotage of product, workplace sabotage, government and or company's facilities sabotage is increasingly emphasized due to the consequences that come after the act. Thus, sabotage is a behaviour envisioned to "damage, disrupt, or subvert the organizations' operations from the personal purpose of the saboteur (sabotage) by creating unfavourable publicity, embarrassment, delays in production, damage to property, destruction of working relationship, or the harming of employees or customers" (Ambrose, Seabright, & Schminke, 2012).

In a developing country such as Nigeria, oil (pipeline) or sabotage is prohibited under the law of the Petroleum Production and Distribution Act (Act 355 of 1990) section 1. However, the Act stipulates and describes a saboteur as "any person who does; aids another person; or incites, counsels or procures any other person, to do anything with intent to obstruct or prevent the production or distributions of petroleum products in any part of Nigeria. Or, any person who wilfully does anything with intent to obstruct or prevent the procurement of petroleum product for the distribution in any part of Nigeria or, does anything in respect of any vehicle or any public highway with the intent to obstruct or prevent the use of that vehicle or that public highway for the distribution of petroleum products" the person found to be guilty of sabotage will be convicted to be sentenced either to death or 21 years' imprisonment (Onuoha, 2018).

This unauthorized act of destruction of pipelines to disrupt the supply of petroleum product for self-purpose and or specific group intent for black-market sales in any dimension are prohibited under Nigerian law. Hence, any person or company involved in such activities is considered to be guilty of economic sabotage (Onuoha, 2008). The question is, have the existing laws worked positively on the intended aim? Notwithstanding, the incidents of oil pollution related to sabotage increase daily despite the existing laws and agencies responsible for monitoring and checking the environmental performance of operating organizations in Nigeria (Shell, 2017). Thus, this amplifies why scholars and writers have frequently stressed its global negative impact

(nations reputation), socio-economic impacts, and effects on the environment (Albert, Amaratunga & Haigh, 2018; Elum, Mopipi, & Henri-Ukoha, 2016; Ndimele et al., 2018).

However, the environment remains a tangible and an aggregate of all external dimensions that affect both living and non-living things and therefore, draws attention to any adverse effects (Olujobi, Oyewunmi, & Oyewunmi, 2018). The effects of sabotage and vandalism activities affect but are not limited to the soil; which is used for daily agricultural purposes in a country such as Nigeria, the air, water as significant sources of living for both animals, plants, fish production, human existence (Mogaji, Sotolu, Wilfred-Ekprikpo, & Green, 2018; Ndeh, Okafor, Akpan, & Olutoye, 2017), and other subsystems associated with the entire global system and our ecosystem.

According to Chibuzor et al. (2014), 40% of the world's oil flows through pipelines that run thousands and or millions of kilometers across unstable areas of the globe. Hence, that influences the access to facilities and the trait of damages (Aishatu et al., 2016). Vandalism and sabotage cases have tremendously and continuously impacted the Nigerian environment and other subsystems through the local refining process (oil bunkering) and its related waves.

Trends in Pipeline Vandalism in Nigeria

According to Junger (2017), Nigeria is getting into more of insecurity, much of the momentum for an economic breakthrough has been lost, in large part because of the increasing rate of oil theft, illegal bunkering, and reckless vandalism of pipelines across the country. The consequences of pipeline vandalism are horrible, which in most cases cause explosions and fires, eventually leading to the loss of lives and properties massively (Junger, 2017).

In the Nigerian oil and gas industry, the effect of pipeline vandalism among others includes huge economic losses from pipeline & plant shutdown, environmental pollution, fire outbreaks usually resulting in loss of lives. Ogbeni (2012) asserted that scarcity & shortage of petroleum products as well as a decrease in electricity supply with the attendant socio-economic problems can also be attributed to pipeline vandalism. In Nigeria, petroleum and associated products are transported through an extensive network of pipelines that run across different locations throughout the country from remote to populated areas. These pipelines are however poorly secured thereby making targets of frequent attacks by vandals (Ogbeni, 2012).

The petroleum products are distributed through the pipeline and bridging systems. The pipeline system conveys the petroleum products from the refineries to the depots. The pipelines may be surface or underground. The pipelines system in Nigeria did not cover the whole nation. It stopped at various terminal depots. The bridging system conveys petroleum products from the depots to filling stations, outlets, jetty, and other retail points. This system is mainly operated by

tankers, trucks, trains, and vessels. Major independent marketers operate within this system to convey products to various parts of the country where pipeline does not cover. The bridging system leads to increased transportation/delivery costs and deterioration of the highway infrastructure (road) through wear and tear, (Adeniyi, 2018). The pipeline system, despite its problems, is still the most effective and efficient means of distribution of petroleum products in Nigeria. The scarcity of petroleum products has been attributed to pipeline vandalism by thieves, multiple damages of pipelines, and leakages, among others (Adeniyi, 2018).

Furthermore, it should be noted that accidents are minimal under pipeline systems but inevitable especially where pipes are old and require replacement, interference by persons of questionable intentions, bursts resulting from the exertion of high pressure, leakages, damages by the rust of pipes, landslides, and erosion that could expose that laid and buried pipes.

Most environmental challenges confronting the country today are related to pipeline vandalism and products handling. Oil spill through pipeline vandalism is a form of terrorism against the oil industry operators, Nigerian Government, and sustainable livelihood of citizens. Consequently, the Nigerian Government and Oil Industry Operators adopted the strategies of joint surveillance of pipeline rights-of-way and strips of land surrounding the pipeline, involving ex-militant leader under the Oil & Gas Pipeline & Waterways (Multi-billion Naira) Surveillance Contract, to stage war against oil pipeline vandalism (Badejo & Nwilo, 2017). In spite of these determined efforts including the huge investments and strategies for effective surveillance of petroleum product pipelines across the country, oil spill incidences resulting from pipeline vandalism continues unabated.

Pipeline Vandalism

Omodanisi, Eludoyin, and Salami (2014) observed that there is about 5120km of pipelines managed by the government through the NNPC, and supplying crude oil contents to facilities all over the country. Although there were laws that stipulated a 47.5m buffer around the oil pipelines, this did not stop vandalism, showing that the measures were inadequate, management of the pipelines was poor, and information tracking of the facilities was inefficient (Omodanisi, Eludoyin, & Salami, 2014).

The Niger Delta region and crude oil pipeline vandalization

The Niger Delta is the center of oil and gas production in Nigeria. It is a vast sedimentary and oil-rich basin of some 70,000km² comprising officially nine states under the Nigerian political structure. This region accounts for the success story of revenue generated by the Nigerian economy since the 1970s. However, in spite of several billion dollars generated from oil exploration and production activities, the region is still the poorest in terms of infrastructural

development. For over five decades, environmental issues such as oil spills and gas flaring have been a feature of oil and gas production in the Niger Delta region. These activities have had an adverse effect on the region's self-sustaining ecosystem, undermining the region's ability to meet its basic needs, which include food, clothing, shelter, safe drinking water, health, and a clean environment (and, above all, the quality of life of the inhabitants of the region) (Onuoha, 2017).

In the view of Olawuyi, (2018) "the region is the underdeveloped and environmentally degraded in Nigeria and the world, as over five decades of exploration and production activities have left the environment severely damaged". Ikelegbe, on the other hand, described events in the region as something of an "ecological warfare" against the Niger Delta. Unsustainable oil and gas exploration and development processes (and their consequences such as oil-well blowouts, oil spillage, gas-flaring, etc) are the primary causes of environmental degradation in the Niger Delta.¹⁶ It is as a result of the above that the region, since the 1990s, has been troubled by restlessness among its younger generation, reported kidnappings of both expert and non expert staff of IOCs, and inter-ethnic crises (Okili, Chukwuma & Sunday, 2013). There has also been a rise in pan-ethnic civil society movements such as the Movement for the Survival of Ogoni People (MASOP), Conference of Traditional Rulers of the Oil Producing States, and Concerned Youths of Oil Producing States, and Delta Oil Producing Communities Association (Okili, Chukwuma & Sunday, 2013). While these groups have engaged successive governments by protesting and entering into dialogue, mostly regarding the plight of the people arising from oil and gas production in the region, it was the activities of groups such as the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), Niger Delta Peoples Volunteer Force (NDPVF) and the recent Niger Delta Avengers (NDA) that seemingly accelerated acts of pipeline vandalism in Nigeria. It is at this junction that the root causes of acts of pipeline vandalism will now be addressed (Okili, Chukwuma & Sunday, 2013)

Causes of crude oil pipeline vandalization

According to Okoli and Orinya, (2013), vandalism is an action involving the deliberate destruction of public or private property within the civic domain. It also denotes willful destruction of public or government property in-keeping with criminal or political intent. In the context of Nigeria, acts of oil pipeline vandalism comprise the willful breaking of oil pipelines with the intent to misappropriate petroleum products, disruption of petroleum production, and the securing of political appeasement (in connection with either IOCs or the government) (Okoli and Orinya, 2013).

It also contemplates the deliberate "breaking" of oil pipelines with the intent to misappropriate petroleum products or to perpetuate what has been described as "acts of sabotage" against the

current administration. Based on the above analysis, and mostly from the points raised by Okoli and Orinya, (2013), it is increasingly apparent that under-investment in, and not sufficient concern for, the Niger Delta region is a strong factor accounting for the current rate of acts of vandalism of crude oil pipelines. This includes, but is not limited to, poverty in the region, what has been described as mismanagement of the oil industry, unemployment in the region, misappropriation of crude oil, and the emergence of what have also been described as “illegal refineries” .

The word “poverty” is defined as “a condition of being poor, and in want” , or “ a general condition of deprivation of need, social inferiority, isolation, physical weakness, vulnerability, powerlessness and economic inequality in the state, and these are prevalent in the Niger Delta region” (Onuoha, 2018:17).

Having regard to the fact that the Niger Delta also hosts the bulk of Nigeria’ s hydrocarbon reserves, poverty appears to be a major reason why people are engaging in acts of oil and gas pipeline vandalism. The significant environmental degradation of some parts of the Niger Delta often means that people do not have the opportunity to practice traditional occupations such as fishing and farming. Consequently, some local communities, where oil pipelines criss-cross their lands, have taken to acts of vandalizing oil pipelines to take oil for sale for economic survival. This was the event that led to the death of over 250 people in Jesse Town in Delta State in 1999 when a vandalized pipeline exploded in flames. In addition, in the period described above, over 477 acts of pipeline vandalism were recorded (Onuoha, 2017).

It has also been emphasized that acts of pipeline vandalism mostly occur in poor courtiers because insufficient legal protection is given to the pipelines (as would be the case in more “ advanced” legal systems). The pipelines have been identified as running through what has been described as “slum areas” and informal settlements in burgeoning cities, which are therefore tempting to the poorest communities that often lack electricity. This is often the case with the Niger Delta region, which continues to witness a rise in the demand for refined petroleum. It is to this end that acts of vandalism take place and the opportunity to “scoop” refined petroleum product by local inhabitants is rarely turned down, even in the face of danger. In the quest for survival and achieving their means of livelihood, people in the region feel that they have no choice but to, on occasions, resort to so-called “violent” means and attack oil and gas installations, allowing them to access the crude oil at will, with the basic interest of using the financial proceeds from the misappropriated oil to alleviate poverty (Nwankwo & Ifeadi, 2013).

Another factor that might be attributed to (or be a cause of) the rise in acts of pipeline vandalism is the current level of unemployment, which has forced many people to take to resort to this kind

of activity, including acts of oil pipeline vandalism and misappropriation of oil as a means for economic survival. Although unemployment is a national issue in Nigeria, confirmed by reports of the Bureau of National Statistics (BNS), unemployment in the Niger Delta appears to be something of a unique set of circumstances given that the region accounts for the bulk of Nigeria's foreign exchange revenue. Of concern is the fact that some of the oil multinationals operating in the region hire the services of manpower personnel from outside the region, while the few that are hired from the region are often disengaged, thereby increasing the number of unemployed among the younger generation (Ugwuanyi, 2013).

Though unverifiable, a possible fall-out from this situation is that the unemployed, disengaged by the IOCs but with technical knowledge of the workings of oil facilities, resort to acts of pipeline vandalism and misappropriation of oil as a means of engaging themselves economically and providing a means of livelihood, (Brume, 2016).

By replicating the British ownership regime of natural resources, the Constitution, rather than, in the author's opinion, empowering the Federal Government of Nigeria to make laws for the overall good governance of Nigeria, vested ownership of all minerals on, and beneath, the subsoil of Nigeria in the Federal Government when it provided;

“... the entire property in and control of all minerals, mineral oils and natural gas in, under or upon any land in Nigeria or in, under or upon the territorial waters and the exclusive economic zone of Nigeria shall vest in the Government of the Federation and shall be managed in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly” (NERC, 2016:10).

The Petroleum Act also vested ownership of similar mineral oil, or their likes, in the government by providing that

“The entire ownership and control of all petroleum in, under or upon any lands to which this section applies shall vest in the state” .

Such ownership applies to all lands, including land covered by water, which:

- is in Nigeria; or
- is under the territorial waters of Nigeria; or
- forms part of the continental shelf of Nigeria; or
- forms part of the Exclusive Economic Zone of Nigeria.

Land in this case also includes “any building and any other thing attached to the earth or permanently fastened to anything so attached, but does not include minerals found on it” .

Third-party acts of tampering and acts of vandalism of pipelines in the Niger Delta are, however, largely responsible for the current issues. This trend of “interfering” with oil pipelines and installations has assumed significant dimensions and has manifested itself in a variety of forms in Nigeria. So-called “bunkering” and attacks on oil vessels and platforms are some of the incidents that have caused concern, resulting in an adverse impact on the environment of the Niger Delta. The fact that these “acts” are seemingly “perpetuated” by the absence of clear deterrent measures, such as the absence of reported prosecutions, has also exacerbated the problem (NERC, 2016).

Consequences of crude oil pipeline vandalism

The ongoing acts of vandalism of oil and gas pipelines (and other oil facilities) have shown that the security of these critical national assets has become a major security challenge. This is because a greater percentage of government revenue is derived from the oil and gas sector. In addition, it must be also emphasised that Nigeria’s power sector largely depends on natural gas for the generation of electricity, thus necessitating that pipelines across the country must be properly secured (Onuoha, 2019).

For instance, the bombing of the Shell Forcados Export Terminal and the acts of vandalism on the Lagos Escravos Pipeline in February 2016 resulted in a shortage of 3,132 megawatts (MW) of electricity. There are a plethora of effects and impacts of acts of pipeline vandalism. Apart from the effect of this on the international price of crude oil, having regard to Nigeria’s global position, Nigeria’s economy, environment, insecurity, and the loss of human lives appear to be the major victims of acts of pipeline vandalism (Onuoha, 2019).

Revenue from crude oil and natural gas is a mainstay of Nigeria’s economy cannot be over-emphasized. Correlating this position, Ajogwu and Nliam (2018) stated, “successive governments ... have continued to maintain this reliance on oil and gas such that the economy has been turned into a mono-cultural one, and inflicted with the Dutch disease” . Estimating loss of revenue to acts of pipeline vandalism is calculated by combining the monetary value of the lost product, cost of pipeline repairs, and the impact of the declaration of “force majeure” . In this regard, records have put losses from 2009-2012 to be approximately ₦165 billion or \$10.9 billion. Within this period, money available to the three tiers of government has also been significantly affected. In the first quarter of 2013 alone, because of a drop in crude oil production arising from ongoing crude oil misappropriation and acts of vandalism along the major pipelines within the Niger Delta, there was a fall in available revenue (Onoja, 2013)

In addition, there was a daily fall in crude oil production, which, during the relevant period, fluctuated between 2.1 and 2.3 million barrels per day (MBPD) compared with the projected estimate of 2.48 MBPD. The fall between actual production and forecast in the first quarter of 2013 resulted in a drop in crude oil revenue as stated above. The loss of oil revenue has also had a negative effect on Nigeria's export of crude oil, which was around two million MBPD as opposed to the budgetary provision of 2.5 MBPD. The country was therefore no longer selling sufficient crude oil to meet its budgetary provisions. These issues were also affecting the government's international crude oil obligations in respect of sales, with the attendant consequences of a rising domestic debt profile (Onoja, 2013).

Strategies to curb crude oil pipeline vandalization

The subject is a multifaceted phenomenon which requires a holistic approach. The issue of piracy as well as pipeline vandalism would reduce if the government introduces capital punishment for the culprits by ensuring that law enforcement agencies are seriously committed to dealing with the pirates as well as the vandals. We cannot completely eradicate these two endemic problems but they are national crisis which only require a tactical approach for us to grow the nation's economy. It is just like a man suffering from HIV/AIDS, the disease isn't curable but it could be managed. Also, a special law court should be established to hear such peculiar cases.

The security agents in charge of the pipelines should be properly screened before deployment to secure the pipelines, they should also be properly taken care of to enable them do their job well because it's likely some of the security agents collaborate with vandals for money, especially oil bunkers. The vandals are mostly jobless youths; the government should look into it properly. Anything asides this, little would be achieved in the stoppage of these vandals. If the Navy protecting the sea borders are well equipped and taken care of, piracy attack will come to a standstill.

It all boils down to the fact that Nigerians are broke, any opportunity to get money, they jump at it and when they get what they want freely, they sell at any price and gain more. What can reduce these problems is if there are jobs in place and if government pays at the right time. Also, our seaports securities should tightened and motor boats for surveillance provided. Not just getting the equipment but the right authorities should be thoroughly taught on how to use them.

The solution to pipeline vandalism is providing adequate security; both from human security to technology security. Strategies need to be implemented because human factors are responsible for all these problems. In as much as we want to curb this issue, we have to implement policies

that will make things fall in place. Even in developed countries, they make use of this security measures to tackle problems. Pipeline attacks can't be stopped but it can be limited and it is still based on security. Maritime policy with sophisticated technologies would help tell where attacks are been carried out, when it was carried out, who carried it out and how it can be resolved. Piracy is recognised as an offence in every nation in the world. There is need to strengthen alliances to defeat piracy attacks across the world, most especially with neighbouring countries.

If the government must extract oil from a particular area, then the indigenes should also be beneficiaries. People vandalise pipelines because of poverty. Most of the people from Bayelsa State are fishermen but if schools and hospitals are built, good roads are done and social amenities provided. Most of the youths will stop vandalising pipelines.

Government needs to put tight securities at the locations where pipelines are located and some form of neighbourhood watch should be adopted because the vandals are within the vicinity. Government should research on new technologies to secure the pipelines and engage locals in developmental programmes to desist from such acts. To reduce pipeline vandalism which is a criminal act, the state of the economy would have to change; money laundering (bribery and corruption), illegal access to firearms should be checked and prevented. In reducing piracy, more funds should be allocated to the adequate training of officers carrying out the duty of guarding our waterways. They should be given adequate facilities needed in combating such menace.

The government need to handle these problems with appropriate hands and should be no more in support of amnesty programmes. They should engage with the local people in the regions where these problems are happening to partner in creating avenues to get the youths busy. The best thing to be done is orientation; the youths need to be put through the fact that the pipeline they are vandalising is actually their money. It is basically tax payers' money that flows through that pipe and is not for someone in government or someone in power, it is for everyone. Youths should be made to know this, so that they know this is not just somebody's property. Secondly, the creation of jobs seems to be the only way out because even the Bible says that an idle mind is the devil's workshop. So when an individual have nothing doing, they will begin to think of all sorts and this includes vandalism. In terms of pirate attacks, I really don't know much about sea pirates but I think the first thing is when you take youth off the streets, you give them something tangible to do; they will think less of how to do wrong things and how to hurt people. The youths provide majority of the manpower, you will hardly see an elderly person being a sea pirate or vandalising pipelines. They don't have the strength for that, that is why am really emphasising on the youths. The brainwork may come from the elderly but the manpower comes from the youth. If the actions of the youths can be curbed, it will go a long way towards reducing these problems.

Oil Bunkering and Illegal oil bunkering

The term ‘bunker’ is derived from a Scottish word, which means a ‘reserved seat’ and is widely used in a different sector to describe an area that safeguards or stores products which could be ammunition, fuel, diesel, or lube oil. Thus, in the context of this research work, which focuses on the crude oil vandalism in the region of study, a fuel bunker is described as a means of storing fuel products on a ship and used for machinery operation, while the process of dealing with bunker fuel is known as bunkering, for example, the process of fuelling the ship with fuel or lube oil product (Onuzuruike, 2018).

Thus, bunkering can be described as the legitimate process whereby a duly licensed operator provides fuel, water, and lubricants for marine services or requests (Mogaji et al., 2018; Onuzuruike, 2018). Hence, making oil bunkering grip a constructive meaning in an overall logic, even though, there is a misconception of the word used to describe oil theft, especially, in Nigeria. According to Vreÿ (2012), oil bunkering is misinterpreted within the Nigerian context due to political, economic, and social controversies embedded in criminal practices. Notably, the practice of oil bunkering which is the process of transporting the filled ship with fuel/oil from one shore to another is categorically different from the process of vandalizing equipment for the bunkering activities. Thus, oil bunkering becomes illegal when unlicensed individuals, groups, or organizations scoop/vandalize the petroleum product in diesel forms, fuel, etc. for its gains.

Accordingly, Onuoha (2018) within the Nigerian context divulged that ‘bunkering’ is an ironic word used to describe oil theft. However, oil bunkering and oil theft is ingeniously the most lucrative private business in the Nigerian petroleum industries in recent times, even though, the activities previously started in the early 1980s (Igbinovia, 2014). Illegal oil bunkering, which is the act of drilling oil pipelines to scoop petroleum product for personal gain is a perpetrated act largely engaged by unlawful groups who are driven by the desire to loot oil products indirectly aiming to sabotage the oil and gas industries or the government (Aishatu et al., 2016). Notably, illegal oil bunkering activity is proven to account for several losses of revenue for both the oil and gas industries and the government since its boom in early 2000 (Igbinovia, 2014; Onuoha, 2008; Shell, 2017).

Nevertheless, Vreÿ (2012); Adishi and Hunga (2017), describe bunker activities in three major levels; small-scale operations that flourish at the local community levels, where the petroleum product is condensate for domestic use and further tapped off for distributions at local usable form. The second practice is where the crude oil product is destined for commercial delivery to barges and ocean traveling tankers for further foreign distribution and destinations (Boris, 2015), while, the third practice is where operating and or delivery companies exceed their legitimate allocations (Adishi & Hunga, 2017). Onuoha (2008) and Vreÿ (2012), stipulate that well-

organized operations of oil bunkers perpetrated by organizations are irreparable. In arguing about illegal oil bunkering activities, Adishi and Hunga (2017) stipulate: “there is a large scale of illegal international trading on crude oil, which is more sophisticated with the use of advanced technologies to tap crude oil and to navigate through the maze of hundreds of creeks, rivers, and streams. This practice has also graduated from ordinary boats and barges to ships and tanker in the high seas which has become extensive and on a large scale since the late 1990s” . Vreÿ (2012) in response to Onuoha (2008) and Adishi and Hunga (2017) connotation highlights that the corruption surrounding oil bunkering activities stretches deeply into the local society, government fabric, and the oil and gas industry and thereby threatens security actions of the citizens.

Thus, these illegal activities are now on an industrial scale and involve international traders and or, which could be termed criminals, commodity traders, and a different network of people within and outside the shores and boundaries of Nigeria (Adishi & Hunga, 2017; Olateju, 2013).

Chibuzor et al. (2014) call for radical action to be taken by a none corrupt governmental regulatory agencies and international oil companies (IOCs) to provide a preventive mechanism for the reoccurrences of the act due to frequent occurrences, given that, in 1999 alone, there were a total of 497 vandalism cases for oil bunkering purposes (Okoli & Orinya, 2013). Further, between 2010 and 2012, a total of about 2,787 pipeline breaks were reported by the Nigerian National Petroleum Commission (NNPC). Thus, these incidents resulted in a loss of approximately 12.53 billion Naira for the nation. Likewise, in 2008 an estimated loss of about 250,000 barrels of oil was lost per day due to ‘theft’ activities, a loss amounting to \$22.5 million US Dollars (Vreÿ, 2012).

Also, between 2009 and 2011, the Nigerian Extractive Industry Transparency Initiative (NEITI) reported a loss of 10.9 billion US Dollars to oil theft (Aishatu et al., 2016). Also, Vreÿ (2012) stipulates that in 2012 there were drops in vandalism and sabotage/thief activities with the estimated loss of 3 million barrels per month compared to preceding years. The reduction, however, was perceived and credited to a particular government security task force deployed against illegal oil bunkering activities (Vreÿ, 2012), even though it lasted for a short period.

Likewise, Aishatu et al. (2016); Adishi and Hunga (2017) stipulates that the activities of oil pipeline vandals for international and or local refining (oil bunkering) resulted in a massive cost of over 174.57 billion Naira in the product losses and repairs of pipelines within ten years, as it increasingly became popular and practiced within Nigeria. Thus, within ten years, a total of 16,083 pipelines breaks were recorded, adding that while 398 pipelines break representing 2.4 percent were due to rupture, 15,685 breaks which were interpreted to about 97.5 % were the activities of unpatriotic vandals (Okoli & Orinya, 2013). However, the growth of this hazardous

business and the scramble for access to oil and gas-related benefits are considered to underpin an environment conducive to the proliferation of an illegal conflict economy and one that operates extensively in the part of the country (Vreÿ, 2012). Also, activities have fuelled long insurgency and have increased armed conflict groups providing militant groups with funds for their operations.

According to Igbinovia (2014), the activities of Nigerian illegal oil bunkering have increased the instability in the world energy markets and also positioned a threat not only to the Nigerian States but to international and oil-bearing communities. Thus, the losses in both production output and financial loss have not been without death incidents of the actors in the process, environmental consequences, and human consequences (Aishatu, Chukwudi, & Hauwa' u; Okoli & Oriya, 2013). Thus, the section below discusses how oil terrorism and environmental terrorism further contribute to environmental devastations.

Oil terrorism and environmental terrorism

Terrorism is an “unlawful use of force or violence against property or persons to intimidate or coerce a government, the civilian population, or any segment thereof, in furtherance of political or social objectives” (Chalecki, 2012). Hence, the word describes such persons who indulge in such activity as “terrorists.” The word terrorism began to have publicity in the 20th century, making terrorist groups wishing to avoid bad publicity began calling themselves “freedom fighters” and “militias” or “militants.” The reform of the word and the concept have been perceived to exist even in the governance system where government-employed terrorist tactics against opponents by calling it “police action” (Chalecki, 2012).

Notwithstanding, the act of oil terrorism and environmental terrorism in the Nigerian context became apparent in early 2005 when the Movement of the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND) blew up a pipeline in Delta state after the arrest of the then leader of the group Alhaji Asari Dokubo (Onuoha, 2018). Since then, oil terrorism and environmental terrorism have increased and influenced environmental damages. The call for the Nigerian Nations natural resources (oil wealth) sharing formula has increased with the view to have a greater share for the Niger Delta communities. Also, Onuoha (2018) stipulates that the activities of freedom fighters or militants are to call for preceding environmental, social, political, and economic justices.

Thus, examples of some blew up by the freedom fighters that have in decades damaged the environment are; the 2005 January blow-up of the Forcados export terminal which cut the supply of the petroleum production of about 100,000 barrels per day. The March 2005 oil pipeline blow-up operated by the Italian company reduced the flow by 65, 000 barrels per day, the 2006

militant struck at an oil vessel at Cawthorowe Channel, killing five soldiers who were escorting the vessel, and later sank the vessels.

Thereafter, the 2007 dreaded attack of three oil pipelines by MEND at the territory of Akassa and Town-Brass (Onuoha, 2018), where some significant attacks were recorded. Even though, the people continuously quest for employment in the oil and gas business to reduce the desperate and frustrated act of destruction. Furthermore, unemployment amongst youth has also created a massive population of idle, frustrated, and desperate young people who are easily manipulated into criminal activities.

Theoretical Framework

Two theories have been selected to buttress this study namely, Frustration-Aggression Theory (FAT) and Routine Activities Theory (RAT).

Frustration-Aggression Theory (FAT)

The study seeks to adopt the “frustration-aggression theory (FAT)” propounded by John Dollard in 1939. It has been expanded by scholars like Berkowitz, Leonard and Yates, Aubry in 1962. Generally, the theory explains that violent behavior is usually caused by the inability of the actor to fulfill his/her socio-economic needs. Those who pursue it use the psychological theories of behavior and motivation to explain why people are involved in violent acts despite the law.

The thrust of the theory is the identification of the difference(s) between what people feel and want, i.e., the want-got rationale, and the expected need satisfaction, i.e., actual need satisfaction. According to Okolo (2018), “this means, where expectation does not meet the actual need, the people are frustrated and would confront those they perceive as responsible for their frustration”. This is where the issue of oil pipelines vandalization in the Niger Delta comes in. The people of the region had had high expectations from the MNOCs when oil and natural gas (ONG) were discovered at Oloibiri in the present Bayelsa State in 1956. They were expecting, among other amenities, regular electricity supply, coastal road networks, efficient health care delivery system, sustainable community development, gainful employment, etc. They are aware that MNOCs usually provide such amenities for their host communities in Europe, and expected same in the Niger Delta. This did not happen, and they protested, especially from the 1990s, and later went underground to vandalize oil pipelines as a way of expressing their frustration over the long years of neglect and underdevelopment. This means the frustration is “induced” by MNOCs and the federal government. Thus, in applying the theory to the circumstances in the Niger Delta, we have to modify it to that, “induced-frustration-aggression theory (IFAT)”.

Routine Activities theory

To accommodate the weakness of actor-network theory, we utilize routine activities theory (RAT) propounded by Felson and Cohen (1979) to explain the modus operandi of pipeline vandalism in Southern Ijaw Local Government in Bayelsa State. RAT is an environmental and location-based criminological theory predicated on 3 basic elements where the convergence of motivated offenders (vandals and collaborators) locate their attractive target (crude products, pressure in the pipelines) in the absence of a capable guardian (lack of surveillance, compromised security apparatus).

Routine activity theory sees the location/place of crime as a major factor influencing crime occurrence due to the convergence in time and place between motivated offenders, suitable targets, and the absence of adequate guardians. These elements explain the occurrence of pipeline vandalism in Southern Ijaw Local Government in Bayelsa State. The terrain in which pipelines are buried is muddy and beneath the soil due to the nature of the product passing through it making surveillance (absence of guardian) difficult for the security outfits while motivated vandals (pecuniary gains) converge to vandalize. Essentially, poor surveillance on Southern Ijaw pipelines and the compromise among security personnel will make pipeline vandalism a huge possibility.

These elements as observed by Cohen and Felson (1979) are suitable to justify why Southern Ijaw vandalism might persist if measures are not emplaced to curb the crime. The motivated offender in this context typifies vandals and their collaborators (those who sponsor the on-field person to vandalize) and who are highly motivated by self-aggrandizement among others factors and makes a plan to vandalize oil pipelines. These motivated individuals, just like other legitimate business individuals invest and ensure necessary steps are taken to reap dividends of their 'investment'. They also act whenever opportunities arise especially when suitable target and unguarded pipelines are available. No matter the volatility or danger involved, oil pipelines are suitable targets for vandals who take solace in the illegal business of sabotaging national interest. Vandalism occurs where guardianship is weak or non-existent. It follows therefore that a formidable and uncompromising security structure would repel and checkmate criminal vandalism.

Research Design

Given the research objectives and questions, this study adopted cross sectional descriptive survey research design because it is mostly used to answer who, what, where, how much, and how many questions. And it helps to compare feelings and opinions of people in general. Hence it is suitable for descriptive and exploratory research of this nature.

Study Area

Southern Ijaw is a Local Government Area under Bayelsa State, Southern part of Nigeria. Its headquarters are in the town of (Oporoma (or Osokoma) in the north of the area at 4°48'17"N 6°04'44"E. The area has a coastline of approximately 60 km on the Bight of Benin. The people and their language are known as Izon. The LGA also has a wide practice of religion such as Traditionalism and Christianity.

It has institutions like the Niger Delta University (NDU), the state's airport in Amassoma and Federal Polytechnic, Ekowe. It is the home of Kolu United FC of Koluama II. The first democratically elected governor, Chief Diepreye Alamieyeseigha (DSP) hailed from the area. It has an area of 2,682 km² and a population of 319,413 at the 2006 census. The postal code of the area is 560. The local government is made up of several towns and villages which include Igbomotoro, Peremabiri, Opuama, Eniwari, Angiama, Diebu, Ondewari, and Aziama.

Population of the Study

The population for the study comprised the local residence, community and opinion leaders, leadership of interest groups, the people of Ijaw Local Government. The specific populations addressed in this study were indigenes (male and female), who were natives of the Ijaw Local Government which were about 319413 according to National Population Census (2019).

Sample Size

In order to get a representation of all the population for this study, the sample size was gotten with the use of Taro Yamane formular:

$$\text{Formula: } n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where:

\overline{n} = number of sample size

N = total population size = 31941

e = level of significance = 0.05

n = 31941

$1+31941(0.05)^2$

n = **354**

Sampling Techniques

The sample were selected through purposive and snowball sampling techniques. In all 354 respondents were randomly selected for the study.

Method of Data collection

The study involved the use of primary data through both qualitative and quantitative methods. The primary source of data collection involved the use of structured questionnaires and In-depth interview.

Instrument for Data Collection

The main instrument of data collection used was questionnaire and was Indept- interview as participants were informed of the purpose of the study and were allowed to choose whether to participate or not. The participants were given enough time to fill out the questionnaire and answer the interview question which was immediately retrieved from them afterwards.

Validity and Reliability of the instrument

To ensure the validity of the instrument, draft copy of the questionnaire were shown to the supervisors who assessed the research questions and the possible ambiguity incomprehension of the questions guide. In addition, the researcher ensured content validity by ensuring adequate coverage of the research questions. From the feedback, some items were modified and corrected for clarity.

Method of data analysis

The technique for the data analysis was Chi-Square with the use of statistical tool I.e Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 23, after collecting data from respondents. The data were presented in tables and questions were processed by coding responses from respondents. The qualitative data were analysed by using content analysis via recording of respondents and transcription.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1 shows that 47.5% of the respondents were male while 52.5% were female. The age distribution of the respondents shows that 68.6% of the respondents were 24 years and above while those between ages 15 and 18 years had the least percentage of 10.5%. Furthermore, 84.2% of the respondents were Christians while 10.5% of the respondents were into Islamic religion. It shows that Christianity is the major religion in the area. Distribution of the respondents by marital status shows that 52.8% were single while 47.2% of them were married

Table 1: The Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency N=354	Percentage %
Sex	Male	168	47.5
	Female	186	52.5
Age	15-18years	37	10.5
	19-23 years	74	20.9
	24 years and above	243	68.6
Religion	Christian	298	84.2
	Muslim	37	10.5
	Traditional	19	5.4
Marital Status	Single	187	52.8
	Married	167	47.2
Occupation	Civil servant	19	5.4
	Self-employed	130	36.8
	Unemployed	38	10.7
	Trading	56	15.8
	Farming	111	31.4
Educational Level	Primary	55	15.5
	Secondary	198	55.9
	Tertiary	76	21.5
	No formal education	25	7.1
Ethnicity	Yoruba	74	20.9
	Igbo	56	15.8
	Hausa	-	-
	Ijaw	224	63.3
Income	Below 30,000	37	10.5
	30,001- 40,000	167	47.2
	40,001 and 50,000	110	31.1
	50,001 and above	40	11.2

Field Survey, 2022

In the occupation category, 36.8% were self-employed, followed by those who were farmers (31.4) while those who were civil servants were 5.4% of the respondents. The table shows that respondents who had secondary education had the highest percentage (55.9%). This is followed by those with tertiary education (21.5%) while only 7.1% of the respondents had no formal education. In the ethnicity category, 63.3% of the respondents were Ijaws followed by those that were Yorubas (20.9%) while the Igbos were 15.8% of the research subjects. Income distribution shows that the more than 80.0% of the respondents earned N50,000.00 and below while the remaining 11.2% earned above N50,000.00

Table 2 shows the distribution of respondents by perceived causes of oil pipeline vandalism. Closed to three-fourth of the respondents were of the opinion that faulty and corrosive pipelines caused pipeline vandalism while roughly one-fourth said no. 89.8% of the respondents said that unfulfilled promises by the Federal government and oil companies, more than three-fourth (74.3%) said corrupt leadership and bureaucracy was the reason for oil pipeline vandalism. Further analysis shows that 84.2% agreed that greed and youthful exuberance, sabotage (58.2%), mechanical failure (78.5%), lack of sense of belonging (52.8%), Poor resource management

(84.2%), inadequate compensation for victim of oil pipeline vandalism (89.8%) and poverty and family expectations (94.6%) were the causes of crude oil pipeline vandalism.

Research Question 1: What are the perceived causes of crude oil pipeline vandalization in the Southern Ijaw Local Government Area?

Table 2: Perceived Causes of Crude Oil Pipeline Vandalism

Items	Yes	No
Faulty and corrosive pipelines are causes of pipeline vandalism?	263 (74.3%)	91 (25.7%)
Unfulfilled expectations/promises by oil-producing companies and the Federal Government are part of the causes of pipeline vandalism.	318 (89.8%)	36 (10.2%)
Corrupt leadership and bureaucracy are part of the causes of pipeline vandalism in Southern Ijaw?	280 (79.1%)	74 (20.9%)
Greed and youthful exuberance are part of the causes of pipeline vandalism in Southern Ijaw.	298 (84.2%)	56 (15.8%)
Sabotage is one of the causes of pipeline vandalism in Southern Ijaw	206 (58.2%)	148 (41.8%)
Mechanical failure is part of the causes of pipeline vandalism in Southern Ijaw	278 (78.5%)	76 (21.5%)
Lack of sense of belonging is one of the causes of frequent pipelines vandalism in Southern Ijaw	187 (52.8%)	167 (47.2%)
Poor resource management is responsible for frequent pipelines vandalism in Southern Ijaw	298 (84.2%)	56 (15.8%)
Inadequate Compensation is responsible for frequent crude oil pipeline vandalism in Southern Ijaw	318 (89.8%)	36 (10.2%)
Poverty and family expectations are responsible for pipeline vandalism?	335 (94.6%)	19 (5.4%)

Field Survey, 2022

Table 3 shows the perception of Southern Ijaw residents about crude oil pipeline vandalism. Relative Importance Index is used to rank the perception accordingly.

$$RII = \frac{\sum W}{A * N} =$$

In a 5 scale Likert variable, Strongly Agree=5, Agree=4, undecided=3, Disagree=2, Strongly Disagree=1

Example, to get the rank for Table 3 row one $RII = \frac{5*225+4*129+3*0+2*0+1*0}{5*354}$

$$= \frac{1641}{1770} = 0.93$$

Where W is the weight given to each factor by the respondents

A = the highest weight in a 5-likert scale question

n = frequency of responses in each category

N =The total number of respondents

The residents of Southern Ijaw Local Government perceived that poverty ranked first as the perceived causes of oil pipeline vandalism (0.94) in the area. This is quickly followed by the desire to make quick money (0.93). Oil pipeline vandalism as source of income (0.92) as well as being a common phenomenon (0.92) ranked 3 respectively. The least cause of crude oil vandalism is self-interest of politicians (0.65) ranked number 7

The findings above have been corroborated by the following interview responses. The first interviewee (IDI) on Perceived causes of crude oil pipeline vandalization in Southern Ijaw is a self-employed lady., She stated thus that:

Infact I remember that the oil and gas contract was amended by Agip company to employ about 100 youths from each community and they promise to be paying them at least N80,000.00 per person on a monthly basis to survive, unfortunately some people have been embezzling the money, with just a few benefiting from the activities these companies. ***(IDI Female, self employed 28yrs, June 2022).***

Another self employed respondent from the study area emphasized that:

Government have not managed the situation of the people very well. They make promises and fail to fulfil them ***(IDI Male, self employed 35yrs, June, 2022).***

The interview conducted gave a better explanation of the perceived cause of crude oil vandalization. For instance, a civil servant stated that:

Neglect From government and oil producing companies is a very serious cause of anger that leads to pipeline vandalization most communities in Southern ijaw local government area are neglected, no good water, no good road and our lands are not good for farming ***(IDI Male, 27yrs civil servant, June, 2022).***

The Interview conducted also supported the data in the table that the above-mentioned points are the Perceived causes of crude oil pipeline vandalization in Southern Ijaw.

Research Question 2: What are the perceptions of Southern Ijaw Local Government residents on crude oil pipeline vandalization?

Table 3: Perceptions of Southern Ijaw Local Government Residents on Crude Oil Pipeline Vandalization

Items	SA	A	U	D	SD	RII	Rank
People engage in crude oil pipeline vandalization to make quick money	225(63.6%)	129(36.4%)	-	-	-	0.93	2
Governments are not making enough effort to curb crude oil vandalization	205(57.9%)	111(31.4%)	38(10.7%)	-	-	0.89	4
Poverty makes people engage in crude oil pipeline vandalization	244(68.9%)	110(31.1%)	-	-	-	0.94	1
Southern Ijaw people see crude oil pipeline vandalization as a major source of income	262(74.0%)	74(20.9%)	-	-	18(5.1%)	0.92	3
People engage in crude oil pipeline vandalization to draw government attention to the community	149(42.1%)	131(37.0%)	55(15.5%)	19(5.4%)	-	0.83	5
Crude oil pipeline vandalization is a common phenomenon among the residents	262(74.0%)	74(20.9%)	-	-	18(5.1%)	0.92	3
People engage in crude oil pipeline vandalization because of peer group influence.	75(21.2%)	169(47.7%)	18(5.1%)	56(15.8%)	36(10.2%)	0.71	6
Crude oil pipeline vandalization is sponsored by a politician to achieve their political aims	36(10.2%)	92(26.0%)	151(42.7%)	75(21.2%)	-	0.65	7
Crude oil pipeline vandalization occurs because of government neglect	168(47.5%)	186(52.5%)	-	-	-	0.89	4

Field Survey, 2022

$$RII = \frac{\sum W}{A * N} =$$

In a 5 scale Likert variable, Strongly Agree=5, Agree=4, undecided=3, Disagree=2, Strongly Disagree=1

Example, to get the rank for Table 4 row one $RII = \frac{5*299+4*55+3*0+2*0+1*0}{5*354} = 1715/1770 = 0.93$

Where W is the weight given to each factor by the respondents

A= the highest weight in a 5-likert scale question

n= frequency of responses in each category

N=The total number of respondents

Table 4 showed the consequences of oil pipeline vandalism. Using relative importance index (RII), The first consequences were that vandalism can lead to large scale death (0.97) and violence (0.97). this is followed by environmental pollution and eco system damage (0.92) while the number three consequence is that oil pipeline vandalism is a threat to the national security (0.87). The least consequence in order of importance is that oil pipeline vandalism can power outage (0.54).

Some questions were asked on the Perception of Southern Ijaw Resident on Crude Oil Pipeline Vandalization. The Interview conducted was answered by a lady, she stated thus:

People engage in crude pipeline oil vandalization because they are angry with the government and oil producing companies. So they vandalized the pipeline to draw their attention. (*IDI Female 27yrs, Self-employed, June, 2022*).

Another interviewee who is also an Ijaw from his own perception, He asserted that;

As a resident of Southern Ijaw LGA, my perception on crude oil pipeline vandalization is that it is causing serious damage to our environment. (*IDI Male, 22yrs Civil Servant, June, 2022*)

Another Interviewee aired his view about perception;

From my own understanding most people engaged in pipeline vandalization to draw government and oil producing companies attention to the communities and also the act is a common occurrence in the region, and it is also influenced by politicians infact I don't think they can stop it (*IDI Male, 26yrs, Trader, June, 2022*).

Research Question 3: What are the consequences of crude oil pipeline vandalization in the Southern Ijaw Local Government Area?

Table 4: Consequences of Oil Pipeline Vandalism in Southern Ijaw Local Government Area

Items	SA	A	U	D	SD	RII	Rank
Pipeline vandalism could lead to large-scale death of several people including the innocent	299(84.5%)	55(15.5%)	-	-	-	0.97	1
The vandalism of crude oil pipelines is regarded as economic sabotage	149(42.1%)	92(26.0%)	113(31.9%)	-	-	0.82	4
Crude oil vandalism leads to wastage of badly needed revenue to finance development in Southern Ijaw and Nigeria at large.	150(42.4%)	111(31.4%)	56(15.8%)	37(10.5)	-	0.81	5
Crude oil vandalism portends great danger and a serious threat to the Nigerians national security.	187(52.8%)	130(36.7%)	19(5.4%)	18(5.1%)	-	0.87	3
Crude oil vandalism aids corruption as the vandalizers often uses the opportunity to exploit he government.	73(20.6%)	187(52.8%)	94(26.6%)	-	-	0.79	6
Environmental pollution and ecosystem damage are serious consequence of Crude oil vandalism in the Southern Ijaw	205(57.9%)	149(42.1%)	-	-	-	0.92	2
Crude oil vandalism could lead to violence especially when surveillance agents clash with vandalizer	298(84.2%)	56(15.8%)	-	-	-	0.97	1
Crude oil vandalism in the southern Ijaw could lead to Fuel scarcity which can affect the nation negatively	55(15.5%)	73(20.6%)	95(26.8%)	131(37.0%)	-	0.63	7
Crude oil vandalism in the Southern Ijaw and Nigeria can led to power outage	54(15.3%)	56(15.8%)	57(16.1%)	187(52.8%)	-	0.54	8
Crude oil vandalism in the southern Ijaw can lead to Population displacement and loss of lives	111(31.4%)	148(41.8%)	57(16.1%)	38(10.7%)		0.79	6

Field Survey, 2022

Table 5 shows the suggested strategies to curb crude oil pipeline vandalism in Southern Ijaw Local Government. Using Relative Importance Index (RII), adequate and well equipped security as well as public education (0.93) ranked as number one. This is followed by proper screening of the security personnel before deployment to secure pipeline facilities (0.89). The third strategy is the inculcation of shared value of integrity and transparency as well as sanctioning of offenders (0.88). the fourth strategy is to engage the youth of the region as many of them are unemployed (0.87). The least ranked strategy to curb oil pipeline vandalism in the area is improved technological (0.74)

$$RII = \frac{\sum W}{A * N} =$$

In a 5 scale Likert variable, Strongly Agree=5, Agree=4, undecided=3, Disagree=2, Strongly Disagree=1

Example, to get the rank for Table 5 row one $RII = \frac{5*224+4*130+3*0+2*0+1*0}{5*354} = \frac{1640}{1770} = 0.93$

Where W is the weight given to each factor by the respondents

A= the highest weight in a 5-likert scale question

n= frequency of responses in each category

N=The total number of respondents.

An Interviewee perspective on the consequences of crude oil pipeline vandalization in Southern Ijaw Local Government Area; he said;

From my own Point of view the community has been invaded by law enforcement agencies in an attempt to capture the vandalizer, the leakage affects the rivers and the fishes die, and the major source gets contaminated. (*Male 25years, Civil Servant, June, 2022*).

Another respondent who had been involved in vandalization before narrated his experience as follows;

It damages the river so the fishermen and the fisherwomen will not be able to go to the river and harvest fish. (*Male 26yrs, Unemployed, June, 2022*).

Another respondent state her opinion as follows;

“It depletes the ozone layer of the environment, It kills the crops of the affected area, It contaminated the water, and it also affect the ecology of the area.. (*Male 26yrs, Unemployed, June, 2022*).

Research Question 4: What are the suggested strategies to curb crude oil pipeline vandalization in Southern Ijaw Local Government Area?

Table 5: Suggested Strategies to Curb Crude Oil Pipeline Vandalism in the Southern Ijaw Local Government Area

Items	SA	A	U	D	SD	RII	Rank
Adequate and well-equipped security and public education	224(63.3%)	130(36.7%)	-	-	-	0.93	1
Adoption of community-based surveillance	186(52.5%)	65(18.4%)	-	103(29.1%)	-	0.79	6
Improved technology involvement	168(47.5%)	63(17.8%)	9(2.5%)	96(27.1%)	-	0.74	7
Empowerment and improved socio-economic activities of the people	236(66.7%)	28(7.9%)	22(6.2%)	7(2.0%)	61(17.1%)	0.81	5
There is also the need to inculcate shared values of integrity and transparency across every level of the governance structure for pipeline security, policy, and enforcement of legal actions on economic saboteurs.	236(66.7%)	57(16.1%)	25(7.1%)	36(10.2%)	-	0.88	3
The federal government should ensure to involve the communities by increasing their stakes in the oil resources.	236(66.7%)	65(18.4%)	7(2.0%)	46(13.0%)	-	0.88	3
The security agents in charge of the pipelines should be properly screened before deployment to secure the pipelines	236(66.7%)	46(13.0%)	-	72(20.3%)	-	0.89	2
The youth of the community should be gainfully engaged because most of them venture into vandalism because of the state of their joblessness	83(23.4%)	236(66.7%)	7(2.0%)	83(23.4%)	-	0.87	4

Field Survey, 2022

Table 5 revealed the suggested strategies to curb crude oil pipeline vandalization in the Southern Ijaw Local Government Area. 100% of the respondent agreed that adequate security and public education is the best way to curb the frequent crude oil pipelines vandalism, 70.9% of the respondents agreed adoption of community-based surveillance is an effective way of curbing the crude oil pipeline vandalism, 65.3% of the respondent fully agreed that improved technology involvement by oil companies will stop crude oil pipeline vandalism, 82.8% of the respondent s agreed that empowerment and improved socio-economic activities will put an end to crude oil pipeline vandalization, 82.8% of the respondent fully agree that there is need to inculcate shared values of integrity and transparency across every level of the governance structure for pipeline

security, 79.7% of the respondents fully agreed that the security agents in charge of the pipelines should be properly screened before deployment to secure the pipelines, and 85.1% of the respondents agreed that the federal government ensures to involve the communities by increasing their stakes in the oil resources among others.

In support of the above, some interviewed respondents suggested their believe strategy to curb crude oil pipeline vandalization in the southern Ijaw Local Government Area as follows; a respondent who is a civil servant suggested that;

The government should set up a separate security to guide the pipelines, engage the youths of the area in different activities, and government should have any agreement on how best to protect pipelines and oil well. (*IDI Male, 24yrs above, June, 2022*).

Another interviewed respondent who is unemployed asserted that:

Federal government and oil companies should pay monthly grants to host communities, also that youths of the community should be gainfully employed, and to engage the youths of the area in different activities. (*IDI Female, 21yrs unemployed, June, 2022*).

The Interview conducted also supported the data in the table that the above-mentioned points are the suggested strategies to curb pipeline vandalization.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One (H₀₁): There is no significant relationship between age and perceived causes of crude oil pipeline vandalization.

Table 6: Showing perceived cause of crude oil vandalization

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Df	t _{cal}	t _{table}
Age	354	46.308	7.287	268	2.876	1.960
Crude oil vandalization	354	43.725	14.38			

P<0.05

Table 6 reveals that t_{calculated} (2.876) is greater that t_{table} (1.960) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between age and perceived cause of crude oil vandalization.

Hypothesis One (H₀₂): There is no significant relationship between religion and perceptions of Southern Ijaw Local Government residents on crude oil pipeline vandalization.

Table 8: perceptions of Southern Ijaw Local Government residents on crude oil pipeline vandalization.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Df	t_{cal}	t_{table}
Religion	354	18.8750	3.78978	268	68.906	1.960
Crude oil vandalization	354	46.3083	7.28737			

P<0.05

Table 8 reveals that $t_{calculated}$ (68.906) is greater than $t_{tabulated}$ (1.960) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between religion and perceptions of Southern Ijaw Local Government residents on crude oil pipeline vandalization.

Discussion of Major Findings

The study examined the perception and consequences of crude oil pipeline vandalism in Southern Ijaw Local Government area. The study shows that more than half of the respondents were female, more than three-fifth were aged 24 years and above, four-fifth were Christians, more than have were single. Nine out of ten respondents were employed and while one-fifth of the respondents had tertiary education.

The study revealed that perceived causes of crude oil vandalism were faulty and corrosive pipelines, unfulfilled promises by Federal government and oil companies, corrupt leadership, greed and youthful exuberance, sabotage, mechanical failure, lack of sense of belonging, poor resource management, inadequate compensation for victim of oil pipeline vandalism and poverty as well as family expectation. However, relative importance index showed that poverty ranked first as one of the major causes of oil pipeline vandalism, sequentially followed by the desire to make money quick, source of income as well as being seen as common phenomenon in the area, government not doing enough to curb the menace, government neglect, peer group influence as well as selfish interest of politician in order of magnitude. This finding corroborate the study by United Nations Development Report (UNDP, 2006) who observed that despite huge financial allocations to Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) Development Commission Oil Mineral Producing Areas (OMPADEC), derivation fund, less is achieved in terms of development of the region due mainly to corruption, mismanagement, lack of justice and human right abuses. The expectations of achieving meaningful development through infrastructural provision, environmental protection are lacking due to poor governance.

The study revealed that the consequences of oil pipeline vandalism in the area of study in order of importance using relative importance index (RII) are (i) large scale death and violence, (ii) environment pollution and eco-system damage, (iii) threat to national unity (iv) economic

sabotage and (v) wastage (vi) gives room for corruption as well as displacement of the population (vii) fuel scarcity and power outage. This finding is in tandem with the views of Njoku (2016) who claimed that Warri North and Warri South-West local government areas in delta state, in 2003, the pipe line vandalization incidence affected about 50 communities these communities included Eketie, Ekporo, Ogbegbe-Eghoruoke and Orere-Yeregbo. These communities were put in a precarious situation as the people could no longer drink the water from the creeks and rivers polluted by the spill. It also affected their livelihood, and made the people live in penury and hunger.

The study revealed that the following strategies can be emplaced to reduce or mitigate oil pipeline vandalism in the study area in order of importance using the relative importance index (RII). These include adequate and well-equipped security as well as public education, screening of security personnel before deployment, inculcation of shared value of integrity and transparency, massive employment for the youth empowerment of the people to improve their socio-economic well-being, adoption of community based surveillance and improved technology.

Conclusion

The study concluded that crude oil pipeline vandalism portends great danger for the economy and security of the nation and so vandalism is caused by poverty, get-rich quick syndrome, vandalism as a source of income, government not paying serious attention to the area, neglect, peer group influence, unemployment and selfish interest of politicians.

Recommendations

- i. Government should provide job opportunities to the teeming youth of the region
- ii. Adequate security should be in place to ensure maximum security for crude oil pipeline facilities in the area.
- iii. Government should improve the socio-economic life of the people of the region by providing social amenities such as good road, pipe borne water, electricity, health facilities in both the rural and urban areas of the region.
- iv. Security personnel to be deployed should be properly screened to ensure that corrupt and fraudulent officers are not deployed to the area.
- v. Oil pipeline vandals or offenders should be punished in line with the relevant law of the nations.

Limitation of the Study

In the course of this study, the researcher encountered a lot of challenges as well as opposition which ranges from financial constraints to time factors. These factors in their ways, slowed down

the speedy progress of this work resulting in the researcher not being able to finish the research work on time as is required. Also, within the study area, the researcher was faced with some other constraints served as limitation to the study and this include lack of accessibility to data, information, and facts concerning the present study due to some reasons or the other, some not willing to give out information that it is to be within the workers. However the researcher have learnt that nothing good comes so easy. Interestingly, the researchers overcome the challenges through resilience and persuasive approach.

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